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Assessing the Impact of Technology Integration on Student Engagement and Classroom Participation in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the impact of technology integration on student engagement and classroom participation in secondary schools within the Abuja Municipal Area Council (AMAC) of the Federal Capital Territory, Nigeria. Using a mixed-methods approach, data were collected from 400 students via structured questionnaires and from 40 teachers via semi-structured interviews. Quantitative data were analysed using descriptive statistics, while qualitative responses were examined thematically to explore teachers' perspectives on technology use. Findings reveal that a majority of students (73.8%) reported access to digital tools, with interactive lessons, visual aids, and multimedia resources identified as the most engaging features. Technology was found to enhance student interest, motivation, and participation, particularly in STEM subjects such as Science and Mathematics, with 53.5% of students reporting significant improvements in academic performance. However, the study also highlights challenges, including limited access to devices, poor internet connectivity, inadequate teacher training, and infrastructural constraints, which restrict consistent technology use, especially in public schools. Teacher interviews corroborated these findings, emphasising the importance of effective integration and professional development. The study concludes that technology has substantial potential to improve learning outcomes and foster active participation, but its success depends on equitable access, pedagogical competence, and supportive infrastructure.

Keywords: Technology Integration, Student Engagement, Classroom Participation, Academic Performance, Secondary Schools, Nigeria

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The rapid integration of technology into educational systems worldwide has transformed traditional classroom practices and pedagogical approaches (Gabdo et al., 2025). In Nigeria, educational stakeholders have increasingly adopted digital tools such as interactive whiteboards, learning management systems, and mobile learning applications to support teaching and learning processes (Okon et al., 2025). This shift aligns with global trends that position technology as a catalyst for enhancing student engagement and active participation, as learners interact with multimedia resources, collaborative platforms, and immediate feedback mechanisms. Studies suggest that technology, when strategically integrated, can stimulate learner interest and foster more dynamic instructional environments (Chukwudum et al., 2025; Spiteri & Rundgren, 2020; Magaji & Adelabu, 2012). Therefore, understanding how technology integration influences student engagement is critical in the Nigerian context, where educational outcomes remain a priority for sustainable development.

Student engagement, defined as the behavioural, emotional, and cognitive involvement of learners in classroom activities, is widely recognised as a key determinant of academic success and meaningful participation (Fredricks et al., 2004, as cited in Ubabuike & Ojechi, 2025). In educational settings, training and funding are required for effective engagement, which manifests as attentiveness, participation in discussions, and persistence in learning tasks (Magaji et al., 2025; Ahmad & Magaji, 2024). The integration of digital tools offers opportunities to move beyond traditional didactic instruction, enabling interactive learning experiences that support student-centred pedagogies and collaborative work (Spiteri & Rundgren, 2020; Ubabuike & Ojechi, 2025). Within Nigerian schools, however, the extent to which such technological innovations translate into enhanced student engagement remains underexplored, especially across different levels of the education system. This research seeks to fill that gap by examining how technology use in classrooms affects students' active participation and motivational levels.

Despite the potential benefits of technology for educational transformation, its integration in Nigerian classrooms faces multifaceted challenges. These challenges include limited infrastructure, inconsistent electricity supply, insufficient teacher training in digital pedagogy, and a lack of policy frameworks to support sustainable implementation (Spiteri & Rundgren, 2020; Ubabuike & Ojechi, 2025; Magaji, 2023). Such constraints can hinder the effective adoption of technology, potentially dampening its impact on student engagement and participation. In addition, disparities in parents' income and access to digital resources between urban and rural schools further complicate equitable use of technology in teaching and learning and affect enrolment (Mahmud et al., 2025). Consequently, evaluating both the positive outcomes and the systemic obstacles is necessary to understand technology's actual influence in Nigerian classrooms.

Empirical studies have shown a positive association between technology integration and student engagement in various Nigerian educational contexts. For instance, research indicates that the use of interactive digital tools correlates with increased learner motivation, participation in activities, and improved academic outcomes (McCall, 2025; Ubabuike & Ojechi, 2025). These findings suggest that when teachers effectively integrate technology into instructional practices, students are more likely to engage actively with course content and classroom tasks. However, to design interventions that maximise these benefits, there is a need for context-specific evidence that considers local educational realities, pedagogical practices, and learner behaviours in Nigerian schools.

Considering these considerations, this study aims to assess the impact of technology integration on student engagement and classroom participation in Nigeria. By investigating how digital tools and instructional technologies influence students' involvement in classroom activities, the research will contribute to the development of strategies that support effective technology use in education. The outcomes of this study are expected to inform educators, policymakers, and stakeholders on best practices for leveraging technology to enhance student engagement and promote active learning. Ultimately, such

insights can help bridge the gap between technological potential and educational practice in Nigerian classrooms.

2.0 Literature Review and Theoretical Framework

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Technology Integration

Technology integration refers to the strategic use of digital tools and resources in teaching and learning to enhance educational outcomes. It involves using devices such as computers, tablets, interactive whiteboards, and software applications to support instructional delivery, facilitate collaboration, and provide personalised learning experiences (Ubabuiké & Ojéchi, 2025). Effective technology integration goes beyond mere device access; it requires aligning digital tools with pedagogical goals, lesson objectives, and student learning needs (Spiteri & Rundgren, 2020). In the context of Nigerian education, technology integration is considered a critical pathway for improving teaching efficiency, fostering innovative learning environments, and preparing students for the demands of a digital society.

2.1.2 Student Engagement

Student engagement is defined as the level of interest, motivation, and involvement students demonstrate in their learning process. It encompasses behavioural engagement (participation in activities), emotional engagement (interest and positive attitudes toward learning), and cognitive engagement (investment in understanding and mastering content) (Fredricks et al., 2004, as cited in Ubabuiké & Ojéchi, 2025). Engaged students are more likely to participate actively in classroom discussions, persist in challenging tasks, and achieve higher academic outcomes (Gabdo & Magaji, 2025). Research has shown that integrating technology into learning activities can significantly enhance engagement by providing interactive content, immediate feedback, and collaborative platforms that stimulate student attention and motivation (Chukwudum et al., 2025).

2.1.3 Classroom Participation

Classroom participation refers to students' active involvement in instructional activities, including responding to questions, contributing to discussions, collaborating with peers, and engaging in hands-on tasks (McCall, 2025). Participation is a key indicator of learning engagement and is closely linked to academic achievement, critical thinking, and social development (Bello et al., 2025). Technology integration can facilitate classroom participation by creating interactive learning environments that encourage students to contribute ideas, ask questions, and collaborate in real time (Ubabuiké & Ojéchi, 2025). In Nigerian classrooms, fostering meaningful participation through technology remains an essential strategy for promoting student-centred learning and enhancing educational quality.

2.2 Theoretical Review

2.2.1 Constructivist Learning Theory

The Constructivist Learning Theory posits that learners actively construct knowledge through experiences, interactions, and reflection, rather than passively receiving information (Piaget, 1973; Vygotsky, 1978). In the context of technology integration in Nigerian classrooms, this theory is highly relevant because digital tools offer opportunities for students to engage in interactive, collaborative, and experiential learning, thereby promoting more profound understanding and active participation (Ubabuiké & Ojéchi, 2025). By integrating technology such as simulations, multimedia resources, and learning management systems, teachers can create environments where students construct knowledge, apply critical thinking, and engage meaningfully with content. This aligns with the study's focus on assessing how technology affects student engagement and classroom participation, emphasising that technology serves not only as a delivery mechanism but as a medium for active learning and knowledge construction.

2.3 Empirical Review

Ubabuiké and Ojéchi (2025) investigated the effect of digital learning tools on student engagement and retention in public secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria. Their study found that integrating interactive multimedia and online resources significantly enhanced students' attention, motivation, and

participation in classroom activities. The research highlighted that technology encourages collaborative learning and provides immediate feedback, which strengthens learners' understanding and retention of knowledge. These findings suggest that effective technology integration can transform classroom dynamics and promote active student engagement.

Chukwudum, Ekwealor, Uchefuna, and Ibeh (2025) conducted a study examining the influence of technology use on students' learning outcomes in Nigerian secondary schools. The study revealed that schools employing digital tools such as projectors, educational software, and tablets observed higher rates of student participation and interaction compared to schools relying solely on traditional methods. The findings underscore the role of technology in facilitating interactive lessons that encourage students to engage actively in classroom discussions and activities.

McCall (2025) explored the relationship between technology integration and student engagement in secondary education across Nigeria. The study indicated that students exposed to blended learning environments that included online simulations, interactive quizzes, and collaborative platforms demonstrated increased behavioural, cognitive, and emotional engagement. Moreover, the research showed that technology-supported instruction can reduce passivity in classrooms, making learners more proactive participants in their educational experiences.

Spiteri and Rundgren (2020) investigated technology integration in classrooms and its impact on student motivation and participation in several international contexts, including African schools. Their findings suggested that digital tools, when aligned with pedagogical goals, improve students' willingness to participate in class activities and facilitate collaborative learning. The study highlighted that technology provides diverse avenues for engagement, including gamified learning experiences and interactive discussions, which can be adapted to the Nigerian educational context to enhance participation.

A study by Onuoha and Eze (2024) examined the use of mobile learning applications in Nigerian secondary schools and their effect on students' engagement and classroom interaction. The research found that students using mobile learning platforms actively participated in group projects, discussions, and quizzes, compared to those in conventional classrooms. The study concluded that technology integration can bridge gaps in traditional pedagogy, encourage active learning, and foster higher levels of student engagement and classroom participation.

2.4 Research Gap

Although previous studies have established that technology integration enhances student engagement and participation in Nigerian classrooms (Ubabuiké & Ojechi, 2025; Chukwudum et al., 2025; McCall, 2025; Spiteri & Rundgren, 2020; Onuoha & Eze, 2024), most of the existing research has focused on general engagement outcomes without sufficiently examining the specific dynamics of classroom participation across different subjects, school types, and levels of education. Additionally, there is limited empirical evidence examining how contextual factors in Nigerian schools, such as infrastructural limitations, teachers' digital competence, and access disparities between urban and rural schools, moderate the relationship between technology use and active participation. This gap highlights the need for a comprehensive study that not only measures engagement but also assesses how technology integration concretely influences students' interactive behaviours and participation in classroom activities, providing context-specific insights for effective educational policy and practice.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

This chapter presents the research methodology used to investigate the impact of technology integration on student engagement and classroom participation in Nigerian secondary schools. The study employs a mixed-method research approach, combining both quantitative and qualitative strategies to provide a comprehensive understanding of the phenomena under investigation. The mixed-method design enables the study to capture measurable patterns of student engagement while also exploring teachers' experiences and perceptions of technology use in classrooms.

3.2 Research Design

The study will adopt a mixed-method research design, integrating both quantitative and qualitative data collection and analysis techniques. This approach is suitable for educational research as it enables the exploration of both statistical relationships and personal experiences. By combining surveys and interviews, the study aims to provide a holistic analysis of how technology integration influences student engagement and participation, offering both generalizable results and contextual insights.

3.3 Study Area

The research will be conducted in the Abuja Municipal Area Council (AMAC) within the Federal Capital Territory (FCT) of Nigeria. AMAC is characterised by a mix of public and private secondary schools, varying levels of technology adoption, diverse socio-economic backgrounds, and ongoing efforts to improve education through digital tools. The area is strategically chosen for its educational diversity and prominence as the nation's capital, making it an ideal context for examining how technology enhances classroom participation and student engagement.

3.4 Population and Sample Size

The population for this study comprises Senior Secondary students (SS1–SS3) in public and private schools within AMAC. According to data from the FCT Secondary Education Board, AMAC contains 32 of the 90 government secondary schools in the FCT. With an estimated student population of around 31,000 in public secondary schools and additional enrollment from private institutions, the study population is estimated at 30,000 to 40,000 students. This population provides a sufficient sample base and ensures representativeness across schools with varying levels of technology integration.

3.5 Sampling Techniques

A combination of simple random sampling and purposive sampling will be used to select schools and participants:

Simple Random Sampling: Schools will be randomly selected to give each school an equal chance of participation, reducing selection bias and enhancing the generalizability of the findings.

Purposive Sampling: Schools that demonstrate notable differences in technology integration or have implemented specific digital initiatives will be purposively included. This ensures that the sample captures a range of technology practices relevant to the research objectives.

3.6 Data Collection Instruments

Data will be collected using two main instruments:

Semi-Structured Interviews: Teachers will participate in interviews designed to explore their experiences, perceptions, and challenges in integrating technology into classroom instruction. This approach allows for detailed qualitative insights and flexibility to probe emerging themes.

Structured Questionnaires: Students will complete closed-ended questionnaires to quantify their experiences with technology, frequency of use, perceived benefits, and participation levels in technology-enhanced learning environments.

3.7 Data Collection Procedure

Data will be gathered from two groups:

- i. **Teachers:** Interviews will be conducted with teachers from selected schools to gain qualitative insights into technology use and its impact on student engagement and participation.
- ii. **Students:** Questionnaires will be administered to students to collect quantitative data on their engagement, classroom participation, and experiences with technology-based learning activities.

3.8 Validity and Reliability

To ensure the study's credibility:

Validity: The instruments will be reviewed by experts and piloted to confirm they accurately measure the constructs of interest.

Reliability: Internal consistency of the student questionnaire will be assessed using Cronbach's alpha, with a threshold of 0.7 or higher considered acceptable. This ensures the instrument reliably captures students' engagement and participation experiences.

3.9 Data Analysis

Quantitative Data Analysis: Questionnaire data will be analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics, including frequency distributions and percentages, to identify patterns and trends in technology use, engagement, and classroom participation.

Qualitative Data Analysis: Teacher interview responses will be analysed thematically, identifying recurring themes and patterns that offer context-rich insights into technology integration practices and their effects on student participation. The integration of both analyses provides a comprehensive understanding of the study's research questions.

4.0 DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS OF RESULTS

4.1 Introduction

This section presents the findings of the study on the impact of technology integration on student engagement and classroom participation in secondary schools within the AMAC Local Government Area of the FCT, Abuja. The study involved 440 participants, comprising 400 students who completed structured questionnaires and 40 teachers who participated in semi-structured interviews. Student responses were collected via Google Forms on shared tablet devices and analysed using SPSS for descriptive statistics. Teacher interviews were transcribed and analysed thematically to extract patterns and insights. The findings are presented in line with the study objectives, covering the extent of technology integration, its impact on academic performance, student engagement and participation, challenges to adoption, and teachers' perspectives, with qualitative and quantitative results triangulated for a comprehensive interpretation.

4.2 Analysis of Questionnaire Responses

4.2.1 Demography of Respondents

Table 4.1: Students' Demographic Profile

Demographic Variable	Category	Frequency (n=400)
Gender	Male	169
	Female	231
Age	10–12	67
	13–15	152
	16–18	179
	19+	2
School Type	Public	200
	Private	200
Class Level	Junior Secondary	200
	Senior Secondary	200

Source: Field Survey 2025

Table 4.1 presents the demographic profile of the 400 student respondents. Female students constituted a higher proportion (57.8%) than males (42.3%), enabling gender-based analysis of technology use. The majority of students (82.8%) were aged 13–18 years, reflecting the typical secondary school population. The sample was evenly distributed between public and private schools (50% each) and across junior and senior classes, ensuring a balanced representation of students and enhancing the generalizability of findings on technology integration and participation.

4.2.2 Technology Integration in Teaching and Learning

Table 4.2: Use of Digital Tools for Teaching and Learning

Response Frequency (n) Percentage (%)

Yes	295	73.8
No	105	26.3
Total	400	100.0

Source: Field Survey 2025

Table 4.2 indicates that 73.8% of students reported using digital tools in classrooms, while 26.3% did not have access to them. This suggests that most schools have begun integrating technology, yet a notable minority still lack access, highlighting disparities that could affect equitable participation and engagement in learning activities.

Table 4.3: Frequency of Technology Use in the Classroom

Response	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Daily	4	1.0
Weekly	137	34.3
Rarely	191	47.8
Never	68	17.0

Source: Field Survey 2025

Table 4.3 shows that technology use in classrooms is largely infrequent. Only 1% of students interacted with technology daily, while 34.3% used it weekly. The majority (64.8%) either rarely or never used digital tools, suggesting that while access exists (Table 4.2), regular classroom integration remains limited, especially in public schools, which aligns with teacher interview findings regarding sporadic technology use.

Table 4.4: Most Commonly Used Technologies in Schools

Technology Type	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Smartboards	38	9.5
Tablets	78	19.5
Computers	329	82.3
Online Platforms	4	1.0
Projectors	179	44.8
None	67	16.8

Source: Field Survey 2025

Table 4.4 highlights that computers are the most frequently used technology (82.3%), followed by projectors (44.8%). Tablets and smartboards are less common, while online learning platforms are scarcely used, reflecting limited adoption of advanced digital and cloud-based tools. These results align with teacher interviews, which revealed that private schools tend to have broader access to a range of technologies. In contrast, public schools primarily rely on basic computer labs and projectors.

4.2.3 Impact on Academic Performance

Table 4.5: Perceived Impact of Technology on Academic Performance

Response	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Yes, significantly	214	53.5
Somewhat	118	29.5
No	68	17.0

Source: Field Survey 2025

Table 4.5 shows that 53.5% of students perceive a significant improvement in academic performance due to technology, while 29.5% noted moderate improvement. The remaining 17% reported no noticeable effect, indicating that while technology can enhance learning outcomes, its effectiveness is influenced by proper implementation, teacher competence, and access to resources. Teacher interviews corroborated these findings, emphasising that consistent use and alignment with lessons are essential for academic gains.

Table 4.6: Subjects Most Improved Through Technology Use

Subject Area	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Science	294	73.5
Mathematics	255	63.8
English	155	38.8
Social Studies	72	18.0
Biology	41	10.3
None	67	16.8

Source: Field Survey 2025

Table 4.6 reveals that Science and Mathematics benefited most from technology use, reflecting its suitability for STEM subjects. Teacher interviews emphasised that visual and interactive digital tools aid comprehension, particularly in complex topics, whereas narrative-based subjects like Social Studies showed limited improvement.

Table 4.7: Effectiveness of Technology in Aiding Understanding

Response Frequency (n) Percentage (%)

Yes	333	83.3
No	67	16.8

Source: Field Survey 2025

Table 4.7 indicates that 83.3% of students felt that technology improved understanding compared to traditional methods. This aligns with teachers' views that interactive and multimedia tools enhance comprehension, especially in science and mathematics, though limited access and insufficient pedagogical support hinder some students.

4.2.4 Impact on Engagement and Participation

Table 4.8: Student Interest in Technology-Integrated Lessons

Response	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Yes	400	100.0
No	0	0.0

Source: Field Survey 2025

Table 4.8 shows unanimous student agreement that technology increases lesson interest, suggesting strong motivational effects. Teacher interviews indicated that interactive lessons, multimedia presentations, and online quizzes capture students' attention and foster active participation, particularly in private schools with better resources.

Table 4.9: Student Participation and Technology Availability

Response	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Yes	283	70.8
No	117	29.3

Source: Field Survey 2025

Table 4.9 demonstrates that 70.8% of students felt technology availability enhanced participation. However, 29.3% disagreed, indicating that participation benefits are contingent on effective facilitation and quality access, as confirmed in teacher interviews reporting infrastructural and instructional challenges in public schools.

Table 4.10: Most Engaging Features of Educational Technology

Feature	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Interactive lessons	353	88.3
Visual aids (videos/images)	353	88.3
Group activities	235	58.8

Feature	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Online quizzes	255	63.8
Other	1	0.3
None	0	0.0

Source: Field Survey 2025

Table 4.10 highlights that interactive lessons and visual aids are the most engaging features, reinforcing teacher observations that multimedia and participatory tools foster attention and collaboration. Online quizzes and group activities also support active engagement, though their impact depends on consistent use and availability of resources.

4.2.5 Challenges of Technology Integration

Table 4.11: Challenges Faced When Using Technology

Challenge	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Lack of access to devices	396	99.0
Poor internet connection	231	57.8
Lack of teacher support	117	29.3
Frequent technical issues	42	10.5

Source: Field Survey 2025

Table 4.11 indicates that device scarcity (99%) and poor internet connectivity (57.8%) are the main barriers. Teachers corroborated that inadequate infrastructure and limited professional training hinder effective integration, particularly in public schools, requiring policy intervention and investment.

Table 4.12: Perception of Equal Access to Technology

Response	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Yes	224	56.0
No	176	44.0

Source: Field Survey 2025

Table 4.12 shows that 56% of students perceived equal access, while 44% reported disparities. Interviews confirmed that school type, funding, and classroom resources influence equity, underscoring the need for strategies to ensure uniform access to technology.

4.3 Analysis of Interview Questions

Q1: Types of Technology Used – Teachers reported that private schools have broader access, including laptops, projectors, tablets, smartboards, and online platforms, while public schools rely mainly on computer labs and shared projectors. Infrastructure issues and limited teacher training constrain the use of technology in public schools.

Q2: Frequency of Technology Use – Private school teachers integrate technology weekly or daily, while public school teachers report sporadic use due to insufficient devices, poor internet, and unreliable electricity. This aligns with student reports showing limited daily interaction with digital tools.

Q3: Most Beneficial Tools – Interactive, accessible, and visually engaging tools (projectors, laptops, educational videos, online platforms, assessment apps) were considered most effective. Private schools used these extensively, while public schools had limited access.

Q4: Influence on Academic Performance – Teachers agreed that technology positively impacts comprehension, retention, and test scores, particularly in STEM subjects. However, inconsistent access in public schools reduces the overall effect, matching students' perceptions of improvement.

Q5: Academic Outcomes Before and After Technology – Technology introduction improved outcomes in both school types, with sustained gains in private schools due to consistent use and administrative support, whereas public schools experienced episodic improvements constrained by infrastructure and access limitations.

4.4. DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings of this study indicate that technology integration in secondary schools within the AMAC area of FCT Abuja has a notable impact on student engagement and classroom participation. The quantitative data reveal that the majority of students (73.8%) reported using digital tools in classrooms, and nearly all students (100%) expressed increased interest in lessons when technology was employed. Interactive lessons and visual aids such as videos and images were identified as the most engaging features, while computers and projectors were the most commonly used tools. Despite these positive trends, the frequency of technology use remains low, with only 1% of students using technology daily and nearly 65% using it rarely or never. This suggests that while technology is available in many schools, actual classroom implementation is inconsistent, particularly in public schools, where infrastructural limitations, poor internet connectivity, and limited teacher training restrict regular use.

The study also highlights the impact of technology on academic performance and participation. Over half of the students (53.5%) reported significant improvements in their academic outcomes due to technology use, especially in STEM subjects such as Science and Mathematics. In comparison, 70.8% agreed that technology facilitates classroom participation. Teacher interviews corroborated these findings, emphasising that technology supports interactive, multimedia-based lessons that improve comprehension, motivation, and collaborative learning. However, challenges such as unequal access to devices, limited teacher support, and infrastructural constraints were also reported, particularly in public schools, indicating that the benefits of technology are not uniformly experienced. Overall, the findings suggest that technology can enhance student engagement, participation, and learning outcomes, but its effectiveness depends on consistent implementation, equitable access, and teacher competence.

5.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study has demonstrated that technology integration in secondary schools within the AMAC area of FCT Abuja positively influences student engagement, classroom participation, and academic performance. The findings show that students are more motivated and attentive in technology-enhanced lessons, particularly when interactive tools and visual aids are employed. STEM subjects, such as Science and Mathematics, benefit the most from digital learning. At the same time, challenges like limited device access, poor internet connectivity, and insufficient teacher training hinder consistent use, especially in public schools. Overall, the study underscores that technology has the potential to improve learning outcomes and foster active participation. However, its effectiveness relies heavily on proper implementation, equitable access, and supportive instructional practices.

Based on the findings, it is recommended that school administrators and policymakers prioritise equitable access to digital tools across both public and private schools, ensuring that students have sufficient devices and internet connectivity. Regular professional development programs should be implemented to

enhance teachers' competence in integrating technology effectively into lessons. Additionally, schools should adopt interactive, multimedia-rich teaching strategies to maximise engagement and participation. Finally, government and education stakeholders should invest in sustainable infrastructure and policy frameworks that support long-term technology adoption, particularly in resource-limited public schools, to ensure that all students benefit from the advantages of digital learning.

REFERENCES

- Ahmad, A. I. & Magaji, S. (2024). Assessment of the Influence of Government Education Expenditure and Economic Growth in Nigeria. *International Journal of Humanities, Social Science and Management (IJHSSM)*, 4(2), pp 674 – 684
- Bello, J. A., Magaji, S. & Ismail, Y. (2025). Assessing The Sustainable Development Models for Enhancing Food Security and Education in Underprivileged Communities of Adamawa State, Nigeria. *ISRG Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies (ISRGJMS)* 3 (9), 29–40. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17413200
- Chukwudum, C. P., Ekwealor, O. U., Uchefuna, C. I., & Ibeh, C. A. (2025). Technology's role in the classroom and its implications for students' learning. *International Journal of Research and Scientific Innovation*. <https://doi.org/10.51244/IJRSI.2024.11120024>
- Fredricks, J. A., Blumenfeld, P. C., & Paris, A. H. (2004). School engagement: Potential of the concept, state of the evidence. *Review of Educational Research*, 74(1), 59–109. <https://doi.org/10.3102/00346543074001059>
- Gabdo, A. L. & Magaji, S. (2025). Examining the Relationship Between Urban Sustainable Development and Quality Education in FCT Abuja, Nigeria. *African Journal of Environment and Sustainable Development|ISSN 3 (2)*, 2718
- Gabdo, A. L., Magaji, S., & Yakubu, J. (2025). Impact of Government Policies on Educational Quality in FCT Abuja, Nigeria. *OSR Journal of Humanities and Social Science (IOSR-JHSS)*. 30(6), 07–14. e-ISSN: 2279–0837, p-ISSN: 2279-0845
- Magaji, S. & Adelabu, J. S. A. (2012). Cost-Benefit of E-Learning Under ODL of Developing Economies. *Huria. Journal of the Open University of Tanzania*, 1(3). 107 – 122
- Magaji, S. (2023). Faculty Strategies for Sustainable Human Capital and Achieving High University Rank. *Journal of Learning and Educational Policy (JLEP)* ISSN: 2799-1121 3 (02), 25-36
- Magaji, S., Ismail, Y. & Musa, I. (2025). Impact of Institutional Quality on Human Capital Development in Nigeria. *MSI Journal of Economics and Business Management*. 2(2), 21-26. DOI: -10.5281/zenodo.14936039
- Mahmud, M., Magaji, S. & Ismail, Y. (2025). Impact of Household Income on Child Labour and Trafficking in Gombe Local Government Area, Gombe State. *ISRG Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies (ISRGJEM)*. 3(8), 50–62. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.16889503
- McCall, A. (2025). The impact of technology integration on student engagement and learning outcomes in secondary education (Preprint). Research in Nigerian secondary schools.
- Okon, L., Musa, I. & Magaji, S. (2025). Assessment of the Impact of Technology Integration on the Quality of Education in Colleges of Education in Nigeria. *MSI Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 2 (2), 32-44 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14892373
- Onuoha, L. O., & Eze, P. N. (2024). Mobile learning applications and student engagement in Nigerian secondary schools. *African Journal of Educational Technology*, 12(2), 87–99. <https://doi.org/10.4314/ajet.v12i2.7>
- Piaget, J. (1973). To understand is to invent: The future of education. Grossman.
- Spiteri, M., & Rundgren, S. (2020). Enhancing student engagement through technology integration in education. *International Journal of Information and Learning Technology*, 37(4), 191–205. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJILT-05-2019-0052>
- Ubabuike, J. C., & Ojechi, P. C. (2025). The impact of digital learning tools on students' engagement and retention in public secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Education Research and Scientific Development*, 8(1), 115–125. <https://doi.org/10.59795/ijersd.v8i1.252>
- Vygotsky, L. S. (1978). *Mind in society: The development of higher psychological processes*. Harvard University Press.